

Original software publication

LFG: An easy-to-use realistic synthetic LandFill Generator

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a Blender add-on named **LFG** that allows for easy, large and realistic, 3D model LandFill Generation. Large datasets of vast, diverse synthetic landfills are hard to come by, and greatly in need for the purposes of developing and evaluating a multitude of algorithms (e.g. waste classification, 3D-reconstruction, volume estimation algorithms) in the context of research against environment crime. Additionally, they can be used alongside UAV simulators for the development of path-planning algorithms. Although there are some 3D models of landfills available on online 3D-model marketplaces, these are often expensive, low-quality, low-variety and unalterable models. LFG offers customizable, expandable options and realistic features tailored for landfill generation and research.

Code metadata

Current code version	v1.0
Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/ElsevierSoftwareX/SOFTX-D-24-00066
Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule	-
Legal Code License	MIT
Code versioning system used	git
Software code languages, tools, and services used	Python 3.10
Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Blender 3.6.0+, OS: Linux, MacOS or Windows
If available Link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/AthanasiosPetsanis/LFG?tab=readme-ov-file#documentation
Support email for questions	athpets@iti.gr

1. Motivation and significance

Environmental crime is currently a serious threat to the European Union [1,2] and the rest of the world. Environmental statistics from 2010 [3] showed that a 40% of waste ends up in landfills even though landfilling is considered a last resort. What is more, large amounts of landfilled waste are biodegradable, which release methane, a potent greenhouse gas. Hazardous waste are also mainly dumped. In 2020, the high numbers persist [4]. The UK has also reported similar problems [5,6]. Legislative Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) are tasked with identifying these landfills and then acquiring on-site evidence such as images, volume, density and types of the illegal waste for judicial purposes. In order to carry out this task, they must rely on the latest technology which involves UAVs, path planning and scanning algorithms, photogrammetry or volumetry techniques and lastly waste identification or even classification.

However, research and development of such tools is hindered by the lack of large datasets on which they can be tested and evaluated. Single waste image datasets exist [7] and have been used for landfill waste classification [8], but do not fully represent the images captured in landfills from UAVs. The same is true for satellite images [9]. This can limit performance of AI models. On the other hand, acquisition missions of real-world data are difficult to conduct since it is often challenging to locate a landfill. Adverse weather conditions, hard-to-reach locations, wildlife (e.g. dogs or birds) and area flight restrictions add more obstacles towards this goal. This results not only in a time-consuming and arduous process, but might also put personnel and expensive equipment at risk. Therefore, it becomes evident that a simulation environment, capable of generating a wide variety of landfills, could really assist the relevant research and development activities.

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Fig. 1. LFG architecture.

There exist many UAV simulators [10] that allow for image capture and processing and many more SfM software for 3D reconstruction [11]. The missing piece, is a tool that can generate realistic synthetic landfills tailored to the needs of each researcher. The alternative, would be to either create one from scratch or search online for 3D assets of landfills. Creating one, requires 3D modeling skills and a lot of time investment while finding one, is often inhibited by the cost of both time and money. Moreover, the researcher would need to repeat the process for every set of landfill specifications they want to run an experiment on.

For the above reasons, we developed a user-friendly Blender add-on that allows the quick generation of large, realistic synthetic landfills based on user-defined options.

We placed emphasis on the realism of the data generated. This involves overcoming a lot of gaps between synthetic and real-world data. Real waste (i) vary in shape and sizes, (ii) form piles with natural collision, (iii) have unique physical properties and (iv) have a unique appearance. We tackled (i) by introducing uniform noise in scale and by including several objects for each waste type. We addressed (ii) with primitive collision bodies and running an animation. For (iii) we handpicked the properties while for (iv) we resolved to textures or objects captured from the real world. Having said that, there is still room for improvement on the quality of materials used and gaps such as objects not being able to break, remain.

Due to the specialized nature of this tool, and to the best of our knowledge we believe it to be the first instance of a synthetic landfill generator. There have been works resembling our own but, none for this specific case. Nakama et al. [12], produced a realistic urban 3D generator based on satellite images. Their work highlights the demand for synthetic data in UAV simulators, but lacks waste generation. One recent Blender product called “Trashed” [13] offers, much like our own approach, procedural generation of waste in an area. However, it is unable to stack them or form piles and the generated objects do not allow for physics interactions. Having faced scarcity of data, Vision-Blender [14] generates synthetic data for computer vision in robotic surgery applications, but again, does not involve waste. Kubric [15], a synthetic data generation pipeline from Google, offers useful functionalities such as high realism and segmentation masks, but currently only contains toy objects and not waste. Importing waste objects is an option, but since it is through a technical coding process of creating a dataset it can be challenging both for us and mostly for the users that

might want to extend them. On the other hand, CAD2Render [16] provides photo-realistic synthetic data generation with Unity3D, making it easier to import datasets. The caveat is that it does not offer easy-to-use tools to create an add-on for our specialized goals compared to the open-source solution and heavily supported Blender application that we chose.

Our work mainly targets simulated UAV missions for landfill inspection that can serve a variety of scientific research. Image acquisition from piles of waste, optimal path planning and volume estimation are the directly impacted fields. In the following sections, we elaborate how we tailored our generator to the intricate demands of the landfill waste research.

2. Software description

LFG compiles, otherwise laborious or expensive processes, into an intuitive interface for the purpose of aiding simulation-based environmental crime tool evaluation with synthetic landfills. It offers options for running different “what-if” scenarios, and a ready-to-use variety of assets.¹ At the same time, it is expandable, meaning the user can add their own instances or collections of objects, scenery or textures.

2.1. Software architecture

As seen in Fig. 1, there are six main Python scripts (blue squares) that constitute LFG. They all utilize the Blender API library for Python called “bpy”. Each of them has a respective button (red dashed squares). Each script is standalone, meaning it can function individually. The interface is also split in 4 segments. The first one is the main path field where the user inputs the path destination of the LFG project, containing all the necessary assets and is needed for the first 3 scripts to work properly (red arrow). *Landscape Generator*, *Load Landscape* scripts and landscape parameters consist the second segment. *Pile Generation* alongside pile parameters are the third segment and finally the last 3 scripts consist the fourth *Utilities* segment.

¹ Credit has been attributed to the creators of all assets [17].

Fig. 2. Currently available LFG assets.

2.2. Software functionalities

LFG's functionalities are split across the six distinct buttons/scripts. Below, we elaborate on the functionalities of each segment.

2.2.1. Landscape generator

A landscape functions as the base on which the waste will be placed. The code must construct a landscape that satisfies real-world expectations in morphology and appearance.

We meet the realistic morphology requirement, by exploiting the pre-installed Blender add-on called "A.N.T. Landscape". It applies noise on the height axis of the terrain, hence creating a rugged surface. By adjusting the parameters of the add-on properly, we created a terrain that is mostly flat, but also included some hills and valleys. We chose this setup empirically, since this is the most common case we have found in the real world. Blender's scalping tool can be used for further changes.

For the realistic appearance requirement, we apply publicly available aerial ground-textures (under CC0 license [18]) from Polyhave [19]. They are aerial, in the sense that they were captured with UAVs and constructed using photogrammetry and at the same time, ground in the sense that they are meant for ground terrains. These currently comprise 11 different textures which you can see in Fig. 2(a). We apply the texture on the terrain by creating a UV map with what is called a "smart UV projection". It is an internal function of Blender that automatically constructs a UV map based on the terrain. Alternatively, the user can choose to load a pre-made landscape 3D model from a drop-down menu. These landscapes were downloaded from Sketchfab under the CC 4.0 license [20]. Currently, 3 landscapes are included.

We merged each terrain's separate components into one joined object for easier positioning of the terrain, and we added a passive rigid body to enable physics and object interactions. Furthermore, we scaled terrains based on scale information whenever available. You can see an example with premade landscapes in Fig. 5(b). Of course, there is always the option to use any other 3D model with a rigid body applied to it.

2.2.2. Pile generator

The second main functionality of our pipeline is pile generation. It allows, with the click of a button, to generate piles in the form of a cone shape (see Fig. 4(a)) with properties according to user input.

The generated wastes of the chosen collection are placed inside the volume of a cone in a grid distribution using the particle system functionality of Blender (Fig. 3). The particle system gives the ability to emit particles of any kind (in this case the waste objects of the chosen collection) from an object (in this case a cone, Fig. 3(a)). By changing the parameters, the user can define the shape and scale of the piles.

Proper selection of parameter values results in scattered waste objects that do not overlap with one another (Fig. 3(c)). We included variation for increased realism by applying randomness in the position, rotation, and scale of the objects. Variety in these properties can also result in more rigorous tool evaluation.

Exploiting Blender's animation capability for pile formation increases realism with the trade-off of increased processing time. In order

to mitigate this drawback, we had to strike a balance between low-polygon rigid bodies for lesser computational cost, but detailed enough representative shapes for each object. We first tested complex hull or mesh shaped polygons on a high-end machine. It took 1 min and 45 s to render 100 frames of 4 cones ("Woods", "Tires", "Kitchen Appliances", and "Plastics") which is a total of 1040 (260 objects for each collection). You can see the start and end of this experiment in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) respectively. Since we aim at large landfill generation, this test proved too expensive and we resorted to primitive shapes that resemble the objects instead. For example, pallets and metal grates used boxes while garbage bags used cones. This time, the same test took only 11 s to complete. For convenience, we added the **Play/Pause** buttons on the interface. In addition, rigid bodies must have realistic object weights and centers of mass. For the volume estimation to work accurately, a closed-surface object is preferable. We checked to see if all the objects satisfied these requirements and modified the ones that did not accordingly. Moreover, we increased the friction value of the surface response for all rigid bodies to 1 and the damping transition/rotation value to 0.6. This helps to stabilize the interacting objects quickly. We gathered 5 collections for a total of 24 objects with attention to realistic textures. These are the "Woods", "Tires", "Plastics", "Metals" and "Kitchen Appliances" (see Fig. 2(c)). There is a sixth collection called "ALL" which combines all objects. All objects were downloaded from Sketchfab under the CC4 license [20] and can be found [here](#).

Each of the texture, landscape or waste collections can be expanded on a whim, as long as the new instances follow our organization conventions. For more details the interested reader can refer to the Github documentation.²

2.2.3. Utilities

The last scripts are under the *Utilities* segment. They offer distinct functionalities for special cases.

First and foremost, the *Volume Estimator* script which is called by the **Estimate Volume** button. The code automatically calculates and displays the total volume ground truth of each pile. We used code from the add-on "3D-print: toolbox" which calculates a 3D object's volume, but our tool does not depend on it being installed. "3D-print: toolbox" is the go-to way for volume calculation in Blender and generally very reliant.

We cannot derive the tool's accuracy because that would require manually measuring the volume of complex shapes. We did, however, validate it with primitive shapes, compared waste volumes with primitive counterparts, tested if random scaling, position, rotation and object duplication affect the volumes as it should and it passed all tests accurately.

When the pile reaches an adequate state, the user should press the **Apply Transformations** button which calls the *Apply Transformations* script. It first selects all the objects belonging to a pile and then applies all transformations. It makes it so that the state the objects reached remains the same throughout the frames. Otherwise, after reloading or undoing, the current state will be lost.

² <https://github.com/AthanasiosPetsanis/LFG>

Fig. 3. Pile generation process.

Fig. 4. LFG. It took 1 min and 45 s to render 100 frames (a to b) with complex collision shapes, while only 11 s with primitive shapes.

Fig. 5. LFG examples. (a) A landscape was first generated with default parameters. 4 main piles consisting of 18 stacked piles were then generated, (b) A premade brick factory landscape was first loaded. 5 individual piles were then generated on top.

Last comes the **Join Objects** button which calls the *Join Objects* script. It joins all objects inside pile collections with the landscape object, making it more convenient to manipulate as one object and because in most cases the wastes do not need to move.

3. Illustrative examples

We showcase the two potential uses of the add-on. One is a landfill based on the generated landscape and the other, is on an existing landscape (see Fig. 5). In either case, the pile generation and formation happens the same way.

In the first example (Fig. 5(a)) we generated both the landscape and the waste. The landscape was generated with default parameters and then we used the scalping functionality of Blender to add bigger hills in desirable spots. The waste consists of 2 main visible piles (woods+plastics and tires) and 2 secondary piles (metals, kitchen appliances). Furthermore, the tires visible pile consists of 6 piles stacked

on top of each other, the woods+plastics consist of 7, the metals of 3 and the kitchen appliances consist of 2. Overall, 2488 objects were generated with a total volume of 221.67 m³. For the completion of the aforementioned landfill, all the processes of generating the objects, placing them and running the animation took a little over 15 min to complete. In this example, piles were formed and stacked progressively until the final result was reached, thus showcasing that our pipeline can be run sequentially. Though, it is also possible to form the piles in parallel as was done in the second example.

Here, we first loaded a 3D brick factory. Then, we placed 5 piles (one for each available waste type) on top of it numbering a total of 3677 objects with 329.22 m³ of volume and ran the animation. The outcome after 120 frames is shown in Fig. 5(b). Animation lasted 53 s and the whole process took no more than 8 min. In both pictures, we highlight the adaptability of this pipeline by placing the waste on different terrain shapes. For example, notice how the tires fill the valleys of each terrain. At a closer look in Fig. 5(b), notice how the tires and metals were placed on top of complexly shaped sand piles.

4. Impact

We argue that LFG is an important milestone towards elevating research for each of the below:

1. Synthetic data:

There is a plethora of open-access waste datasets [7], but these are mostly captured in set-up environments which degrades realism. Even in data captured from UAVs, they never include large heaps or piles or open dump-yards [21]. As mentioned before, it is also demanding to acquire synthetic landfills online. In contrast, our approach tackles these challenges and the following are concrete examples for which LFG can prove useful. One is the generation of synthetic UAV images for waste classification. Classifying individual waste objects is highly sought-after [8,22–25] whereas, in the context of landfills, it is scarce even though waste segregation and detection of hazardous types is important. This is because training a model to classify landfill waste requires numerous annotated images [26] and manual labeling can be even more challenging [27]. The high visual fidelity of LFG, coupled with a UAV simulator, could augment UAV imagery datasets.³ Furthermore, LFG names each object according to its waste type, thereby effortlessly providing the labels. It is important to note, that LFG does not currently support the automatic orthophoto or 3D point cloud segmentation, although such a useful functionality is planned for future versions. Another direction is that of satellite images for the case of illegal landfill identification [9]. By placing synthetic landfill orthophotos on top of real satellite images, researchers can generate additional training data. When captured with the GSD (i.e. ground sampling distance) that is typical in satellite imagery, synthetic from real data become even harder to distinguish.

2. Volume estimation:

In court, the volume of waste plays a key role in the final verdict. Therefore, it is of high interest to legislative authorities to estimate the volume of landfills confidently and accurately. The obstacle researchers face towards this end, is acquiring the ground truth for volume with which they can evaluate their modules. Since it is near impossible to manually calculate the volume, they rely on TLS (Terrestrial Laser Scanner) or GNSS-RTK (Global Navigation Satellite System with Real Time Kinematics) systems. It is shown that volume estimations based on UAVs are not far from TLS [28] and total station [29] based estimations, but the question of how far away these measurements are from the ground truth still remains [30–32]. This is especially true considering TLSs cannot always cover the top part of the piles. On the other hand, simulations offer that advantage, and that is the purpose of the *Volume Estimator* script. This is the first time, the ground truth of volume for landfills can be consistently provided.

3. UAV Path planning and 3D reconstruction:

Plenty of researches optimize UAV path planning with respect to 3D reconstruction. Typically, they evaluate viewpoint optimization algorithms on synthetic scenes via programs such as Blender [33] or UnrealEngine [34]. Davide Marelli et al. [35] created an add-on in Blender for evaluating 3D reconstruction which could work hand-in-hand with LFG. Other times, a UAV simulator [10] (e.g. AirSim [36]) is employed [37] allowing for realistic image acquisition. In most cases, researchers optimize the paths mainly for structures like buildings. Landfills, however, have different morphology, significantly more details and vegetation or structures obstructing the view. Landfill occlusion

is especially problematic for authorities trying to identify hazardous waste or estimate the volume. LFG lays the foundation to research ways that combat the aforementioned challenges. Moreover, 3D reconstruction research could benefit from more available data [38].

5. Conclusions

We presented LFG, a robust 3D landfill generator add-on for Blender that targets research for environmental crime tool evaluation. We described its functionalities and demonstrated its current potential. We also argued about how crucial it can be in many types of research fields. Blender is free, easy to use, intuitive, flexible and due to its popularity there is a large availability of technical support. Consequently, it was our preferred software for 3D modeling and can quickly be adopted by researchers. In the PERIVALLON [39] project we aim to develop all the aforementioned research tools and we intend to evaluate them through LFG.

Notably, this is just version 1.0 which sets the foundations for the tool. For future work, we plan to greatly expand on the collections of objects grouped by waste types as categorized according to the European Union's Methodology Documents [40] and (more specifically the EWC-Stat categories document) and automatically segment in the 3D model or orthophoto output. In addition, we plan to alleviate processing even further and include synthetic GCPs (Ground Control Points) which significantly improve 3D-reconstruction.

Overall, we believe LFG is a big enabler towards combating environmental crime with innovative research.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Thanos Petsanis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Athanasios Ch. Kapoutsis:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Elias B. Kosmatopoulos:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2024.101936>.

Data availability

Both code and data used have been shared with respective links inside the research paper.

³ Note that LFG can benefit augmentation of landfill imagery, but would have little to no effect on single waste object detection.

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